

06/23

VOLUME II

Firelogue

Cross-sector dialogue
for Wildfire Risk Management

NEWSLETTER

What is Firelogue

Firelogue is a European project, funded by Horizon 2020 under the Green Deal call, that brings together expertise from all around Europe when it comes to Wildfire Risk Management.

From researchers to civil society organisations, Firelogue's partners have the experience, knowledge, together with a forward-thinking attitude that has placed them at the front and centre of all aspects related to WFRM to contribute with solutions and knowledge exchange.

15 Partners 4 Years 9 European Countries

FIRELOGUE PARTNERS

Learn more about Firelogue, by clicking [here](#)

Firelogue Working Groups

The Project consists of **5 Working Groups (WG)**, each one dedicated into exploring different aspects of WildFire Risk Management (WFRM).

Let's learn more about them!

Civil Protection Working Group

#WG_CivilFirelogue possesses key areas of expertise that revolve around wildfires, e.g. in areas of fire response, prevention, and planning. The team's expertise extends to wildfire training and the establishment of effective command and control systems.

Civil Protection Working Group is led by **TIEMS**, with **12 dedicated participants** working together to ensure the safety and well-being of our communities and collaborates with other related projects, namely: FIRE-RES, SILVANUS, TREEADS, FirEUrisk, and Nemausus.

Future Goals

EU level:

- **Influence set-up** of new EU Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) modules.
- **Monitor their interoperability** (with national systems), when EUCPM is activated
- **Discuss the Requirements** for the Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network

National level:

- **Existing approaches/gaps** and options for **knowledge sharing**
- Interaction of responders with **prevention activities**
- **Protection** of Critical Infrastructures
- **Structural recommendations** for strategical posture in order to receive EUCPM help
- Aspects of **evacuation & involvement** of the public

civil-protection@firelogue.eu

#WG_InfraFirelogue is led by **KEMEA** - Center for Security Studies. It consists of **14 dedicated members**, who are committed to ensuring the **safety and resilience of critical infrastructure**.

Members of the WG are part of the Innovation Actions, ie. FIRE-RES, SILVANUS, and TREEADS. The partners include the Cyprus Civil Defense, Ukrainian Lviv State University of Life Safety, University of Aegean, USDHS, World Bank, GSN Science, ENEA, IIASA, and other independent experts.

Future Goals

- Create a “**white paper**” with **policy recommendations** regarding infrastructure upgrade and protection, towards minimization of fire ignitions, as well as societal and environmental impact by wildfires and service interruption
- **Exchange with peers** across and beyond projects
- **Exchange lessons learnt and best practices**
- **Discuss and learn** about topics of other interrelated WGs
- **Create an interested and active community in WFRM** with particular interest in infrastructure upgrade and protection

infrastructure@firelogue.eu

#WG_EnvironFirelogue, led by the CTFC - Forest Sciences Centre of Catalonia, consists of **15 dedicated members** who are passionate about **protecting and preserving our natural environment**. It consists of various participants, including the team's **Innovation Actions, FIRE-RES, SILVANUS, TREEADS**, and other fire-related projects **Pyrolife, RESONATE, ResAlliance, and FoRISK (Forest Europe)**.

The key areas of expertise within the working group revolve around landscape resilience, climate change adaptation, wildfire risk management, disaster risk management, land and forest management, as well as biodiversity conservation. Through the collective knowledge and experience, the WP is dedicated to promote sustainable practices and safeguard the ecological balance.

Future Goals

- Promote **cross-sector dialogue** around specific topics.
- Identify **synergies and conflicts** to avoid policy disfunctions and enhance cooperation.
- Provide **policy (and/or technical) recommendations** from an environmental perspective in a Firelogue White Paper.
- Develop **thematic WildFire Risk Management** European communities.
- **Exchange** lessons learned and best practices, discuss and learn about topics of other WGs yet highly interrelated, etc.
- **Promote networking** within and across wildfire risk management community and other related disciplines and sectors.

Societal Working Group

#WG_SocietalFirelogue is led by VOST - Portugal, and consists of **11 dedicated members**, who are committed in addressing the **societal impact of wildfires**. The team is in close collaboration with participant Innovation Actions, including **Fire-Res, Silvanus, and TREEADS**, in order to tackle the challenges faced by our communities.

External partners include ISA, SOS Arganil, Pyrolife, CTFC, ISC UL, and ISIG. Their diverse perspectives enrich our discussions and initiatives.

The key areas of expertise revolve around wildfire risk management, sociology, land management, and disaster response. The aim is to understand and mitigate the social and environmental impact of wildfires, while also focusing on effective land management practices and disaster response strategies.

Future Goals

- **Bring together** representatives from Innovation Actions, practitioners, policy experts and citizens to discuss
- **Communicate** the need for a more clear and concise communication with citizens
- **Highlight** the importance of involving citizens in the decision making process when designing new policies or structural behavioral changes
- **Foster partnerships** to enhance wildfire prevention and response efforts.
- **Review and critique** existing wildfire policies at national and European levels

wgsocietal-info@firelogue.eu

Insurance Working Group

#WG_InsuranceFirelogue, led by IIASA, is dedicated to **explore the intersection of insurance and wildfire risk management**. With representatives from Firelogue Partners and Firelogue Innovation Actions such as **TREADS, FIRE-RES, CMCC, IIASA, and CTFC**, we strive to develop **innovative solutions in the insurance sector**.

External partners include **Marsh McLennan, InsuResilience, Zurich Insurance, Global Quake Model, Guy Carpenter, SwissRe, WTW, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche Istituto per la Bioeconomia, University of Lisbon, Leitha, ORRAA, Forest Re, Wharton, consorseguos.es, and Mitiga Solutions**. Their diverse perspectives enrich our discussions and initiatives.

The team focuses on the evolving landscape of wildfire risk and its implications for the insurance industry. Through collaboration and knowledge-sharing, the aim to develop innovative insurance solutions that address the challenges posed by wildfires.

Future Goals

- Options for **equitable wildfire insurance and risk transfer**
- **Insurance and risk transfer incentives** as well as requirements for wildfire risk reduction, notably also through nature-based solutions (NBS)
- **Accessibility, affordability and availability** of safety nets for low-income households and vulnerable businesses in wildfire risk areas
- **Responsibility for reducing wildfire risks through measures**, including nature-based solutions (NBS) such as restoring degraded ecosystems or controlled burns and other cost-effective solutions

insurance@firelogue.eu

Firelogue Platform

In the context of the Firelogue Project, the “Lessons on Fire powered by Firelogue” platform was launched in March 2023, designed to connect services and stakeholders. It is intended to be an area for information, innovative solutions and services provided by the Innovation Actions (IAs) about the WildFire Risk Management (WFRM) community

Become an active member of the platform, interact with other experts and stakeholders and submit relevant news, events, case studies, scientific papers and more.

Discover this online WFRM Community!

Visit the platform by clicking [here](#)

#EUFireProjectsUnited

#EUFireProjectsUnited is a dynamic initiative by Firelogue to bring together several innovative fire-related projects in Europe. Launched in April 2022, this initiative brings together communication experts from **Firelogue**, **FIRE-RES**, **SILVANUS**, **TREADS**, **FirEUrisk**, **SAFERS**, **FireLINKS** and **FIRE-IN**. In January 2023, two more projects became part of #EUFireProjectsUnited; **PyroLife** & **FireAdapt**.

Through #EUFireProjectsUnited, the projects are collaborating to create common dissemination actions and joint participation in fire-related events. This initiative has already made an impact, with the creation of communication materials for fire-related international days and participation in numerous events throughout Europe.

Use our hashtag **#EUFireProjectsUnited** to mention us on twitter.

If you want to join this initiative send us an e-mail to:

info@firelogue.eu

Title: [EUFireProjectsUnited]

[Learn more about EUFireProjectsUnited here.](#)

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